

THE ADJACENCY-PELL-HURWITZ NUMBERS

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Abstract

In this paper, we define the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers by using the Hurwitz matrix of order $4m$ which is obtained by the aid of the characteristic polynomial of the adjacency-Pell sequence. Firstly, we give relationships between the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers and the generating matrices for these sequences. Further, we obtain the Binet formula for the $(2m - 1)$ -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers. Also, we derive relationships between the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers and permanents and determinants of certain matrices. Finally, we give the combinatorial and exponential representations of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers.

1. Introduction

It is well-known that the Pell sequence is defined by the following equation:

$$P_{n+1} = 2P_n + P_{n-1}$$

for $n > 0$, where $P_0 = 0$, $P_1 = 1$.

The adjacency-type sequence is defined in [3] by an mn -order recurrence equation:

$$x_{nm+k}^{n,m} = x_{nm-n+1+k}^{n,m} + x_k^{n,m}$$

for $k \geq 1$, where $x_1^{n,m} = \dots = x_{nm-n+1}^{n,m} = 0$, $x_{nm-n+2}^{n,m} = 1$, $x_{nm-n+3}^{n,m} = \dots = x_{nm}^{n,m} = 0$ and $n, m \geq 2$.

Karaduman and Deveci defined the adjacency-Pell sequence as follows:

$$a_{m,n}(mn+k) = 2a_{m,n}(mn-n+k+1) + a_{m,n}(k)$$

for the integers $k \geq 1$, $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 4$, with initial constants $a_{m,n}(1) = \dots = a_{m,n}(mn-1) = 0$ and $a_{m,n}(mn) = 1$ [5].

Consider the k -step recurrence sequence:

$$a_{n+k} = c_0a_n + c_1a_{n+1} + \dots + c_{k-1}a_{n+k-1}$$

where $c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{k-1}$ are real constants. Earlier, Kalman [8] derived a number of closed-form formulas for some generalized sequences via the companion matrix method as follows:

If the companion matrix A is defined by

$$A = [a_{i,j}]_{k \times k} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \\ c_0 & c_1 & c_2 & & c_{k-2} & c_{k-1} \end{bmatrix},$$

then

$$A^n \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_{k-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_n \\ a_{n+1} \\ \vdots \\ a_{n+k-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

for $n \geq 0$.

Consider f a real polynomial of degree n given by

$$f(x) = a_0x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + \dots + a_{n-1}x + a_n.$$

Hurwitz [7] introduced the matrix $H_n = [h_{i,j}]_{n \times n}$ associated to f as follows:

$$H_n = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_3 & a_5 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_0 & a_2 & a_4 & & & & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & a_1 & a_3 & & & & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & a_0 & a_2 & \ddots & & & 0 & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & a_1 & & \ddots & & a_n & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & a_0 & & & \ddots & a_{n-1} & 0 & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & 0 & & & & a_{n-2} & a_n & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & & & a_{n-3} & a_{n-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & a_{n-4} & a_{n-2} & a_n \end{bmatrix}.$$

Several authors have used homogeneous linear recurrence relations to deduce miscellaneous properties for a plethora of sequences; see for example [4, 6, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19]. In particular, Deveci and Shannon defined the adjacency-type numbers and examined their structural properties [3]. The adjacency-Pell numbers, their miscellaneous properties and applications in groups were studied by Deveci and Karaduman in [5]. In the present paper, we define the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers by a recurrence relations of order $4m$, ($m \geq 2$) and give their generating matrices, Binet formulas, permanental, determinantal, combinatorial, exponential representations, and we derive a formula for the sums of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers.

2. The Main Results

For $m \geq 2$ and $n = 4$ it is clear that the characteristic polynomial of the adjacency-Pell sequence is

$$p(x) = x^{4m} - 2x^{4m-3} - 1. \tag{2.1}$$

Then by (2.1), we see that the Hurwitz matrix $H_{4m} = [h_{i,j}]_{4m \times 4m}$ associated to a polynomial p is

$$[h_{i,j}]_{4m \times 4m} = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } i = 2k - 1 \text{ and } j = k + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 2m, \\ -1 & \text{if } i = 2k \text{ and } j = k + 2m \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 2m, \\ 1 & \text{if } i = 2k \text{ and } j = k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We define the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers by using the Hurwitz matrix H_{4m} as shown:

$$x_{4m+u}^{(k,m)} = -2x_{4m-2k+1+u}^{(k,m)} + x_{4m-2k-2+u}^{(k,m)} \tag{2.2}$$

for the integers $u \geq 1$, $m \geq 2$ and $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, with initial constants $x_1^{(k,m)} = \dots = x_{4m-1}^{(k,m)} = 0$ and $x_{4m}^{(k,m)} = 1$. Here $x_i^{(k,m)}$ is the i th term of the k th sequence according to the constant m .

By (2.2), we may write

$$M_m^{(1)} = [m_{i,j}^{(1)}]_{4m \times 4m} = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$M_m^{(\lambda)} = [m_{i,j}^{(\lambda)}]_{4m \times 4m} =$$

$$\begin{matrix} & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & (2\lambda + 2) \text{ th} \\ & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & \downarrow \\ & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & & \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & & & & & \dots & & & & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & & & & & & \dots & & & & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & & & & & \dots & & & & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & & & & \dots & & & & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & & & & \dots & & & & & & & & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & & \vdots & & & & & & & & & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & & & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & & & & & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & & \dots & & & & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & & \dots & & & & & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & & & & & & & & & \ddots & \ddots & & & & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & & & & & & & & & & \ddots & \ddots & & & & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & & & \dots & & & & & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & 0 & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & \dots & & & & & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \end{matrix}$$

for $2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$ and

$$M_m^{(2m-1)} = [m_{i,j}^{(2m-1)}]_{4m \times 4m} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & & \cdots & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & & \cdots & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & & \ddots & \ddots & & \\ 0 & \cdots & & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \\ 0 & \cdots & & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \end{bmatrix}.$$

We call matrix $M_m^{(\alpha)}$ the α -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz matrix of size $4m \times 4m$.

By an inductive argument on τ , we obtain

$$\left(M_m^{(1)}\right)^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} x_{4m+\tau}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(1,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(1,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-5}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(1,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-6}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-5}^{(1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(1,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

for $\tau \geq 1$,

$$\left(M_m^{(\lambda)}\right)^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} x_{4m+\tau}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau+1}^{(\lambda,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau+2\lambda-2}^{(\lambda,m)} \\ x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau}^{(\lambda,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau+2\lambda-3}^{(\lambda,m)} \\ x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau+2\lambda-4}^{(\lambda,m)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda+1}^{(\lambda,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(\lambda,m)} \\ x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda}^{(\lambda,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(\lambda,m)} \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix} E,$$

for $\tau \geq 1$ and $2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$, where E is the following $4m \times (4m - 2\lambda + 1)$ matrix:

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-3}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-4}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-3}^{(\lambda,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2\lambda-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\left(M_m^{(2m-1)}\right)^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} x_{4m+\tau}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau+1}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{8m+\tau-4}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} \\ x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{8m+\tau-5}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(2m-1,m)} \\ x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{8m+\tau-6}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-5}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-4}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(2m-1,m)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{\tau+3}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+4}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_\tau^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+2}^{(2m-1,m)} \\ x_{\tau+2}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+3}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau-2}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_\tau^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+1}^{(2m-1,m)} \\ x_{\tau+1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau+2}^{(2m-1,m)} & \cdots & x_{4m+\tau-3}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau-2}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_{\tau-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & x_\tau^{(2m-1,m)} \end{bmatrix},$$

for $\tau \geq 3$. Let $m \geq 2$ and let $S_i^{(k,m)} = \sum_{i=1}^t x_i^{(k,m)}$ such that $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$. We introduce matrix $H(k, m)$ by

$$H(k, m) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & & & & \\ 0 & M_m^{(k)} & & & \\ \vdots & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix}$$

for $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$. Note that $H(k, m)$ is a square matrix of size $(4m + 1) \times$

$(4m + 1)$, and it can be shown by induction that:

$$(H(1, m))^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ S_{\tau+4m-1}^{(1,m)} & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-2}^{(1,m)} & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-3}^{(1,m)} & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-4}^{(1,m)} & (M_m^{(1)})^\tau & & & \\ 0 & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } \tau \geq 1,$$

$$(H(\lambda, m))^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ S_{\tau+4m-1}^{(\lambda,m)} & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-2\lambda-2}^{(\lambda,m)} & (M_m^{(\lambda)})^\tau & & & \\ 0 & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } \tau \geq 1 \text{ and } 2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$$

and

$$(H(2m - 1, m))^\tau = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ S_{\tau+4m-1}^{(2m-1,m)} & & & & \\ S_{\tau+4m-2}^{(2m-1,m)} & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & \\ S_{\tau+2}^{(2m-1,m)} & (M_m^{(2m-1)})^\tau & & & \\ S_{\tau+1}^{(2m-1,m)} & & & & \\ S_\tau^{(2m-1,m)} & & & & \end{bmatrix} \quad (\tau \geq 3).$$

Lemma 2.1. *The equation $x^{4m} + 2x^3 - 1 = 0$ does not have multiple roots for any integer $m \geq 2$.*

Proof. Let $q(x) = x^{4m} + 2x^3 - 1$ and suppose v is a multiple root of $q(x)$. Since $q(0) \neq 0$, it follows that $v \neq 0$. Then, the hypotheses $q(v) = 0$ and $q'(v) = 0$ imply $v^{4m-3} = -\frac{3}{2m}$ and $v^3 = \frac{2m}{4m-3}$, respectively. It follows that $v^3 > 0$ and $v^{4m-3} < 0$, inequalities that cannot hold simultaneously for $m \geq 2$. This is a contradiction resulting from our assumption that v is a multiple root, which concludes the proof of the lemma. $\square$

Let $q(v)$ be the characteristic polynomial of matrix $M_m^{(2m-1)}$. Then, $q(v) = v^{4m} + 2v^3 - 1$, a clear fact because $M_m^{(2m-1)}$ is a companion matrix.

Let $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4m}$ be the eigenvalues of $M_m^{(2m-1)}$. By Lemma 2.1, we know that these are $4m$ distinct numbers. Let $V_m^{(2m-1)}$ be the following Vandermonde matrix:

$$V_m^{(2m-1)} = \begin{bmatrix} (v_1)^{4m-1} & (v_2)^{4m-1} & \dots & (v_{4m})^{4m-1} \\ (v_1)^{4m-2} & (v_2)^{4m-2} & \dots & (v_{4m})^{4m-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ v_1 & v_2 & \dots & v_{4m} \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Denote by $V_m^{(2m-1)}(i, j)$ the matrix obtained from $V_m^{(2m-1)}$ by replacing the j th column by

$$C_m^{(2m-1)}(i, j) = \begin{bmatrix} v_1^{\tau+4m-i} \\ v_2^{\tau+4m-i} \\ \vdots \\ v_{4m}^{\tau+4m-i} \end{bmatrix}.$$

We can give the generalized Binet formula for the $(2m - 1)$ -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers with the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1. For the matrix $\left(M_m^{(2m-1)}\right)^\tau = \left[m_{i,j}^{(2m-1,\tau)}\right]_{4m \times 4m}$, for $\tau \geq 3$,

$$m_{i,j}^{(2m-1,\tau)} = \frac{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}(i, j)}{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}}. \tag{2.3}$$

Proof. Consider the integer $\tau \geq 3$ to be fixed. Since $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4m}$ are distinct, the matrix $M_m^{(2m-1)}$ is diagonalizable. Then, $M_m^{(2m-1)}V_m^{(2m-1)} = V_m^{(2m-1)}D_m$, where $D_m = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4m})$. Since $\det V_m^{(2m-1)} \neq 0$, we can write

$$\left(V_m^{(2m-1)}\right)^{-1} M_m^{(2m-1)} V_m^{(2m-1)} = D_m.$$

Then, the matrix $M_m^{(2m-1)}$ is similar to D_m and so

$$\left(M_m^{(2m-1)}\right)^\tau V_m^{(2m-1)} = V_m^{(2m-1)}(D_m)^\tau.$$

We can now easily establish the following linear system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} m_{i,1}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_1)^{4m-1} + m_{i,2}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_1)^{4m-2} + \dots + m_{i,4m}^{(2m-1,\tau)} = (v_1)^{n+4m-i} \\ m_{i,1}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_2)^{4m-1} + m_{i,2}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_2)^{4m-2} + \dots + m_{i,4m}^{(2m-1,\tau)} = (v_2)^{n+4m-i} \\ \vdots \\ m_{i,1}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_{4m})^{4m-1} + m_{i,2}^{(2m-1,\tau)}(v_{4m})^{4m-2} + \dots + m_{i,4m}^{(2m-1,\tau)} = (v_{4m})^{n+4m-i} \end{cases}.$$

The numbers in formula (2.3) are solutions of the last linear system. □

Theorem 2.1 gives immediately:

Corollary 2.2. *Let $x_\tau^{(2m-1,m)}$ be the τ th element of the $(2m - 1)$ -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz sequence, then*

$$\begin{aligned} x_\tau^{(2m-1,m)} &= \frac{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}(4m, 4m)}{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}} = \frac{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}(4m - 1, 4m - 1)}{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}} \\ &= \frac{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}(4m - 2, 4m - 2)}{\det V_m^{(2m-1)}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we consider the permanent representations of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers.

Definition 2.1. *Let $M = [m_{i,j}]$ be $u \times v$ real matrix and let $r^1, r^2, \dots, r^u$ and $c^1, c^2, \dots, c^v$ be respectively, the row and column vectors of M . If r^α contains exactly two non-zero entries, then M is contractible on row α . Similarly, M is contractible on column β provided c^β contains exactly two non-zero entries.*

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_u$ be row vectors of the matrix M and let M be contractible in the α^{th} column with $m_{i,\alpha} \neq 0, m_{j,\alpha} \neq 0$ and $i \neq j$. Then the $(u - 1) \times (v - 1)$ matrix $M_{ij:\alpha}$ obtained from M by replacing the i^{th} row with $m_{i,\alpha}x_j + m_{j,\alpha}x_i$ and deleting the j^{th} row and the α^{th} column is called the contraction in the α^{th} column relative to the i^{th} row and the j^{th} row.

The permanent of a u -square matrix $A = [a_{i,j}]$ is defined by

$$\text{per}(A) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_u} \prod_{i=1}^u a_{i,\sigma(i)},$$

where the summation extends over all permutations σ of the symmetric group S_u .

In [1], Brualdi and Gibson showed that $\text{per}(A) = \text{per}(B)$ if A is a real matrix of order $u > 1$ and B is a contraction of A .

Let $n \geq 4m$ and let $X(k, (m, n)) = [x_{i,j}^{m,n,k}]$, $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, be the $n \times n$ super-diagonal matrices defined using the following cases:

1. $i = \gamma$ and $j = \gamma + 2k - 2$ for $1 \leq \gamma \leq n - 2k - 1$,
2. $i = \gamma, j = \gamma + 2k + 1$ for $1 \leq \gamma \leq n - 2k - 1$, and $j = \gamma - 1$ for $2 \leq \gamma \leq n$,
3. otherwise.

$$x_{i,j}^{m,n,k} \begin{cases} -2 & \text{if case (1) applies} \\ 1 & \text{if case (2) applies} \\ 0 & \text{if case(3) applies} \end{cases},$$

where m is as in the definition of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers. Then we have the following theorem.

Theorem 2.3. *For $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, we have*

$$\text{per}(X(k, (m, n))) = x_{4m+n}^{(k,m)}.$$

Proof. Consider the matrix $X(1, (m, n))$. We will use induction on n . Assume the equation holds for $n \geq 4m$. Then we must show that the equation $\text{per}(X(1, (m, n))) = x_{4m+n}^{(1,m)}$ holds for $n + 1$. If we expand $\text{per}(X(1, (m, n)))$ by the Laplace expansion of permanent according to the first row, then we obtain

$$\text{per}(X(1, (m, n + 1))) = -2 \text{per}(X(1, (m, n))) + \text{per}(X(1, (m, n - 3))).$$

Since $\text{per}(X(1, (m, n - 3))) = x_{4m+n-3}^{(1,m)}$, we obtain

$$\text{per}(X(1, (m, n + 1))) = -2x_{4m+n}^{(1,m)} + x_{4m+n-3}^{(1,m)} = x_{4m+n+1}^{(1,m)}.$$

The proofs for $2 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$ are similar to the above and are omitted. □

Let $n \geq 4m$. Now we define the $n \times n$ matrices $Y(k, (m, n)) = [y_{i,j}^{m,n,k}]$, $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, using the following cases:

1. $i = \delta$ and $j = \delta + 2k - 2$ for $1 \leq \delta \leq n - 2k - 1$,
2. $i = \delta$, $j = \delta + 2k - 2$ for $1 \leq \delta \leq n - 2k - 1$, and $j = \delta - 1$ for $2 \leq \delta \leq n$,
3. otherwise,

With these three cases in mind we now define the desired matrix:

$$y_{i,j}^{m,n,k} = \begin{cases} -2 & \text{if case (1) applies} \\ 1 & \text{if case (2) applies} \\ 0 & \text{if case(3) applies} \end{cases},$$

where m is as in the definition of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers. In the next theorem we obtain another permanental representation.

Theorem 2.4. *For $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, we have*

$$\text{per}(Y(k, (m, n))) = x_{4m-2k-2+n}^{(k,m)}.$$

Proof. Consider matrices $Y(\lambda, (m, n)) = [y_{i,j}^{m,n,\lambda}]$, $2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$. We will use induction on n . Suppose that the equation holds for $n \geq 4m$. Then we must show

that the equation holds for $n + 1$. If we expand the $\text{per}Y(\lambda, (m, n))$ by the Laplace expansion of permanent according to the first row, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{per}(Y(\lambda, (m, n + 1))) &= -2 \text{per}(Y(\lambda, (m, n - 2\lambda + 2))) + \text{per}(Y(\lambda, (m, n - 2\lambda - 1))) \\ &= -2x_{4m-4\lambda+n}^{(\lambda,m)} + x_{4m-4\lambda+n-3}^{(\lambda,m)} = x_{4m-2\lambda+n-1}^{(\lambda,m)} \end{aligned}$$

for $2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$. Thus, the conclusion is obtained.

The proofs for the matrices $Y(1, (m, n))$ and $Y(2m - 1, (m, n))$ are similar. $\square$

We now consider the sums of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers by using their permenantal representations. Let $n > 4m$ and suppose that $Z(1, (m, n))$, $Z(\lambda, (m, n))$, ($2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2$) and $Z(2m - 1, (m, n))$ are the $n \times n$ matrices defined by

$$Z(1, (m, n)) = \begin{bmatrix} & & \begin{matrix} (n-4) \text{ th} \\ \downarrow \end{matrix} & & & & \\ & & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & Y(1, (m, n-1)) & & & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2.4}$$

$$Z(\lambda, (m, n)) = \begin{bmatrix} & & \begin{matrix} (n-\lambda-4) \text{ th} \\ \downarrow \end{matrix} & & & & \\ & & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & Y(\lambda, (m, n-1)) & & & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix} \tag{2.5}$$

and

$$Z(2m - 1, (m, n)) = \begin{bmatrix} & & \begin{matrix} (n-6) \text{ th} \\ \downarrow \end{matrix} & & & & \\ & & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & Y(2m - 1, (m, n - 1)) & & & \\ & & \vdots & & & & \\ & & 0 & & & & \end{bmatrix}. \tag{2.6}$$

Then we have the following theorem.

Theorem 2.5. For $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$, let the $n \times n$ matrices $Z(k, (m, n))$ be as in (2.4), (2.5) and (2.6). Then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{per}(Z(1, (m, n))) &= \sum_{\varepsilon=1}^{n+4m-1} x_{\varepsilon}^{(1,m)}, \\ \text{per}(Z(\lambda, (m, n))) &= \sum_{\varepsilon=1}^{n+4m-2\lambda-3} x_{\varepsilon}^{(\lambda,m)}, \quad (2 \leq \lambda \leq 2m - 2), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\text{per}(Z(2m - 1, (m, n))) = \sum_{\varepsilon=1}^{n-1} x_{\varepsilon}^{(2m-1,m)}.$$

Proof. Consider the matrices $Z(2m - 1, (m, n))$. Expanding $\text{per}(Z(2m - 1, (m, n)))$ with respect to the first row, we have

$$\text{per}(Z(2m - 1, (m, n))) = \text{per}(Z(2m - 1, (m, n - 1))) + \text{per}(Y(2m - 1, (m, n - 1))).$$

By Theorem 2.3 and the inductive argument on n , we easily complete the proof.

The proofs for $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 2$ are similar to the above and are omitted. $\square$

A matrix M is called *convertible* if there is an $n \times n$ $(1, -1)$ -matrix K such that $\text{per}M = \det(M \circ K)$, where $M \circ K$ denotes the Hadamard product of M and K .

Let $n > 4m$ and let W be the $n \times n$ matrix defined by

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

It is easy to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{per}(X(k, (m, n))) &= \det(X(k, (m, n)) \circ W), \\ \text{per}(Y(k, (m, n))) &= \det(Y(k, (m, n)) \circ W) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\text{per}(Z(k, (m, n))) = \det(Z(k, (m, n)) \circ W)$$

for $n > 4m$ and $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$.

Consider the $n \times n$ matrix

$$C = C(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & c_2 & \cdots & c_n \\ 1 & 0 & & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

For detailed information about the companion matrix, see [11, p.69] and [12, p.284].

Theorem 2.6. (Chen and Louck [2]). The (i, j) entry $c_{i,j}^{(\tau)}(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ in the matrix $C^\tau(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ is given by the following formula:

$$c_{i,j}^{(\tau)}(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) = \sum_{(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)} \frac{t_j + t_{j+1} + \dots + t_n}{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_n} \times \binom{t_1 + \dots + t_n}{t_1, \dots, t_n} c_1^{t_1} \dots c_n^{t_n} \tag{2.7}$$

where the summation is over nonnegative integers satisfying $t_1 + 2t_2 + \dots + nt_n = \tau - i + j$, $\binom{t_1 + \dots + t_n}{t_1, \dots, t_n} = \frac{(t_1 + \dots + t_n)!}{t_1! \dots t_n!}$ is a multinomial coefficient, and the coefficients in (2.7) are defined to be 1 if $\tau = i - j$.

Now we give the combinatorial representations for the $(2m - 1)$ -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz sequence by the following Corollary.

Corollary 2.7. Let $x_\tau^{(2m-1, m)}$ be the τ th element of the $(2m - 1)$ -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz sequence such that $\tau \geq 3$ and $m \geq 2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} x_\tau^{(2m-1, m)} &= \sum_{(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{4m})} \frac{t_{4m-2} + t_{4m-1} + t_{4m}}{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_{4m}} \times \binom{t_1 + \dots + t_{4m}}{t_1, \dots, t_{4m}} (-2)^{t_{4m}-3} \\ &= \sum_{(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{4m})} \frac{t_{4m-1} + t_{4m}}{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_{4m}} \times \binom{t_1 + \dots + t_{4m}}{t_1, \dots, t_{4m}} (-2)^{t_{4m}-3} \\ &= \sum_{(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{4m})} \frac{t_{4m}}{t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_{4m}} \times \binom{t_1 + \dots + t_{4m}}{t_1, \dots, t_{4m}} (-2)^{t_{4m}-3}, \end{aligned}$$

where the summation is over nonnegative integers satisfying $t_1 + 2t_2 + \dots + (4m)t_{4m} = \tau$.

Proof. In Theorem 2.6, if we choose $n = 4m$ and $i = j$ such that $4m - 2 \leq i, j \leq 4m$, then the proof follows from (2). □

Now we give the generating function of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers.

Let

$$g^{(k, m)}(y) = x_{4m}^{(k, m)} + x_{4m+1}^{(k, m)}y + x_{4m+2}^{(k, m)}y^2 + \dots + x_{4m+u-1}^{(k, m)}y^u + x_{4m+u}^{(k, m)}y^{u+1} + \dots$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} 2y^{2k-1}g^{(k, m)}(y) &= x_{4m}^{(k, m)}2y^{2k-1} + x_{4m+1}^{(k, m)}2y^{2k} + x_{4m+2}^{(k, m)}2y^{2k+1} \\ &\quad + \dots + x_{4m+u-1}^{(k, m)}2y^{2k-1+u} + x_{4m+u}^{(k, m)}2y^{2k+u} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

and

$$y^{2k+2}g^{(k, m)}(y) = x_{4m}^{(k, m)}y^{2k+2} + x_{4m+1}^{(k, m)}y^{2k+3} + x_{4m+2}^{(k, m)}y^{2k+4}$$

$$+ \dots + x_{4m+u-1}^{(k,m)} y^{2k+2+u} + x_{4m+u}^{(k,m)} y^{2k+2+u+1} + \dots .$$

Thus, we have

$$g^{(k,m)}(y) + 2y^{2k-1} g^{(k,m)}(y) - y^{2k+2} g^{(k,m)}(y) = x_{4m}^{(k,m)} y^{4m-1}.$$

By the definition of the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers, we obtain

$$g^{(k,m)}(y) = \frac{y^{4m-1}}{1 + 2y^{2k-1} - y^{2k+2}},$$

where $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$ and $0 \leq y^{2k+2} - 2y^{2k-1} < 1$.

Now we give an exponential representation for the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers.

Theorem 2.8. *For $1 \leq k \leq 2m - 1$ and $0 \leq y^{2k+2} - 2y^{2k-1} < 1$, the k -adjacency-Pell-Hurwitz numbers have the following exponential representation:*

$$g^{(k,m)}(y) = y^{4m-1} \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(y^{2k-1})^i}{i} (y^3 - 2)^i \right).$$

Proof. Since

$$\ln g^{(k,m)}(y) = \ln \frac{y^{4m-1}}{1 + 2y^{2k-1} - y^{2k+2}} = \ln y^{4m-1} - \ln (1 + 2y^{2k-1} - y^{2k+2})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \ln (1 + 2y^{2k-1} - y^{2k+2}) &= \ln (1 - (y^{2k+2} - 2y^{2k-1})) \\ &= -[(y^{2k-1})(y^3 - 2) + \frac{1}{2}(y^{2k-1})^2 (y^3 - 2)^2 \\ &\quad + \dots + \frac{1}{i}(y^{2k-1})^i (y^3 - 2)^i + \dots] \\ &= - \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(y^{2k-1})^i}{i} (y^3 - 2)^i \right), \end{aligned}$$

we have

$$\ln g^{(k,m)}(y) - \ln y^{4m-1} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(y^{2k-1})^i}{i} (y^3 - 2)^i.$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\ln \frac{g(x)}{y^{4m-1}} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(y^{2k-1})^i}{i} (y^3 - 2)^i.$$

The last formula implies the one in the text of the theorem, thus concluding the proof. □

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